

MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITE WITH PRINTED SENSORSPengzhe Yang ^{1,2}, Yu Jia ^{1,3}, Xueyong Wei ² and Yu Shi¹¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Thornton Science Park,
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China,Email: seanwei@mail.xjtu.edu.cn³ Mechanical Engineering and Design, Aston University, Birmingham B4 7ET, UKEmail: yu.jia.gb@ieee.org**Keywords:** multifunctional composite; inkjet printer; printed sensor**ABSTRACT**

Battery management system (BMS) is a critical component for electric and hybrid electric vehicles (EV) as it determines the battery efficiency and safety of application. The continuous in situ temperature monitoring is critical in order to ensure the safe and efficiency operation of the battery system for electric vehicles. The use of multi-functional composite as the battery enclosure not only improves the mechanical properties with further reduction of the weight for electric vehicles, but also implements integrated sensing capabilities for monitoring purpose. This paper reports the use of Dimatix inkjet printer (DMP-2850) to print thermal temperature sensors on composite battery enclosure to achieve integrated in situ monitoring of battery temperature. The thermal temperature sensors are first printed on resin coated Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) substrate and then the printed sensors are co-cured with glass fiber prepreg to achieve multifunctional composite for sensing. This result demonstrates a new method to integrate composite with printed sensors, without the need of adding discrete and bulky sensor systems, and the printed temperature sensor can compare with commercially available Pt thermal resistance temperature sensors.

1 INTRODUCTION

Compared with other commonly used batteries, lithium-ion batteries enjoy a high power density, high energy density, long service life, and environmental friendliness, which have been widely used as reliable energy sources in the area of consumer electronics. However, lithium-ion batteries for electric vehicles have high capacity and large serial-parallel numbers, which, coupled with such problems as safety, durability, uniformity and cost, imposes limitations on the wide application of lithium-ion batteries in the vehicle [1]. Therefore, lithium-ion batteries must be used within a safe and reliable condition, which is restricted by temperature. The performance, life, and safety of lithium-ion batteries are all affected by their operation and storage temperatures [2-5]. The recoverable power and capacity will be reduced significantly when these batteries are operated or stored at temperatures above 50°C. Hence, it is imperative that lithium-ion batteries used in EV applications should be held at temperatures below 50°C [6].

Battery management system (BMS) which need to manage hundreds of or thousands of single cells by monitoring them. It is a critical component for electric and hybrid electric vehicles as it determines the battery efficiency and safety of application [7-9]. BMS of electric vehicles is comprised of kinds of sensors, actuators, controllers that need to protect the battery from being damaged and make the battery work in the appropriate voltage and temperature range. A real time temperature monitoring in-situ is therefore significant to accelerate the development of electric vehicles by building a reliable battery system.

The use of multi-functional composite as the battery enclosure not only improves the mechanical properties with further reduction of the weight for electric vehicles, but also implements integrated

sensing capabilities for monitoring purpose. This paper describes how printed sensors could be additive manufactured using inkjet-printing and integrated with a glass fibre composite substrate. Moreover, the experimental result verifies that the printed sensor integrated with composite could effectively monitor the temperature.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD DETAILS

2.1 Maskless inkjet-printed sensors on PET

Inkjet printing and screen printing are two different processes for printed sensors. Due to inkjet printing is a mask-less drop-on-demand technique which allows for the deposition of ink layers on flexible or rigid substrates [10]. Another advantage of inkjet printing is that the printer can deposit more than one ink on the substrate. That allows the user easily to add kinds of different materials on the substrate or some flexible prepreg and integrate sensors on composites to produce a multifunctional composite.

The thermal sensors were fabricated using a Fujifilm Dimatix DMP 2850 as maskless material inkjet printer. Figure 1 shows the printer capable of printing precise nanoparticle ink, such as silver nanoparticles ink and graphene ink. The printer uses a piezoelectric element to drive voltage through the nozzles, ejecting droplets on the substrate according to the pre-edited voltage waveform [11], which would decide the size of the droplets. A number of parameters [12] need to be optimized, such as cartridge temperature, substrate temperature, gain of the nozzle voltage, frequency of the nozzles, drop spacing, etc. The silver nanoparticles ink used is Smart 'Ink S-CS01130 conductive ink [13] which has low curing temperature for printing on flexible substrates, good adhesion on polyethylene terephthalate (PET) substrate and various curing process including photonic, low vacuum oven and thermal.

Figure 1: FUJIFILM Dimatix Materials Printer DMP-2850.

The parameters of the printer were set to a jetting frequency of 5 kHz and a meniscus vacuum set to 3 [14], and the substrate temperature set to 60°C in order to obtain smooth edges of the pattern. Note that the high temperature of the substrate will make the organic solvents in the ink evaporate faster that would cause the nozzles clogged and damage the cartridge. The cartridge temperature was set to 30 °C, which needs to be adjusted to change the viscosity of the ink to get the desired jetting performance. The drop spacing which is the center to center distance of the drops of the printer can be adjusted between 5 to 254 μm in one micron increments by changing the cartridge mounting angle. If the drop spacing were too large, the line printed would be disconnected, as shown in Figure 2(c)-(d) where the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) comparison for various drop spacing scenarios were shown. According to this result, the diameter of the droplet is about 55 μm . In this study, a drop spacing of 50 μm should be ideal for this application.

After printing, the substrate should be thermally sintered to remove organic solvents in the ink and fuse the Ag nanoparticles together to form conductive tracks. A curing process for consolidation of this nanosilver ink was performed in the oven at 120 °C for 20 minutes. The overview and the SEM observations of the thermal sensor are shown in Figure 3. And the average thickness of the silver line was 0.8 μm [14].

Figure 2: Electron microscopy (SEM) pictures of silver ink drop deposited on polyethylene terephthalate (PET) for four different drop spacing, when the drop spacing is larger than 50 μm, the droplets will be separated.

Figure 3: SEM pictures of the sensor's structure and details.

2.2 Integration of printed sensor with composite

Considering the ignorable thickness of sensor's substrate PET (about 150 μm) and the structure of the sensor is very small, the co-curing was performed for integration with glass fiber/epoxy prepreg in the consistent programmed curing cycle. First, using the silver conductive adhesive to lead two wires from the pads of the thermal temperature sensor. After paving full layup of the prepregs, put the pre-printed sensor on the one edge of the top layer prepreg, as shown in Figure 4, the co-curing process was then followed up. During the co-curing process, the resin in the prepreg will flow and cover the sensor to form a protective layer that can protect the sensor from damage and oxidation. The sensor and the composite are integrated and will not cause any defect of composite.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of the composite structure with printed sensor. The left one and right one depict the cross-section view and top view of the structure respectively. The layer with twill patterns is glass fiber prepreg and the brown square sheet demonstrate the printed sensor.

3 RESULTS

The schematic of multifunctional composite integrated with thermal temperature sensor is shown in Figure 5. The overall structure of the sensor is smaller than 5 mm, which means the composite can integrate multiple different sensors with different functions avoiding adding any discrete and bulky sensor system and realizing multifunction composite. Thanks to co-curing, the sensor was protected by the inherent resin of prepreg, which can prevent the sensor from oxidation under the impact of the environmental or damage by external loadings.

Fig.5. The sensor was integrated with the composite and covered by the resin in the prepreg. The right one depicts the enlarged graph of the sensor part and ruler shows the length of printed sensor is smaller than 5 mm.

Figure 6 shows the relationship between resistance and temperature of printed thermal temperature sensor. It was found that the sensitivity was almost linearly varied by $1.225 \Omega/^{\circ}\text{C}$ from 30°C to 70°C and the temperature coefficient can be calculated using the following equation:

$$\alpha = \frac{R - R_{ref}}{R_{ref}(T - T_{ref})} \quad (1)$$

where α , R and T are the temperature coefficient, the resistance and the temperature respectively, and R_{ref} is the resistance at temperature T_{ref} . The temperature coefficient of $3.19\text{E-}3/^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 30°C can compete with commercially available Pt thermal resistance temperature sensors that is $3.851\text{E-}3/^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 0°C . The greatest advantage of this is easier to integrate with composite for wider applications of streamlined structure such as aircraft, wind turbine and etc.

Fig.6. Resistance of the sensor for temperature between 30°C and 70°C , which can cover the maximum temperature the battery can stand. The sensitivity of the printed temperature sensor reported here is $1.225 \Omega/^{\circ}\text{C}$.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Composite battery housing for electric vehicles requires the lightweight and high mechanical strength, in order to improve the mileage and enhance the reliability and safety by monitoring the working conditions. This paper explores the additive manufacturing approach by inkjet printing the thermal temperature sensor on PET and integration with glass fiber composite for real-time temperature monitoring of battery to eliminate thermal runaway risks for enhanced safety. The multifunctional composite with temperature sensor was experimentally proved to be sensitive to measure the temperature and therefore demonstrated a promising avenue by additive manufacturing sensors using inkjet printing technology for integration with composite avoiding to add any discrete and bulky sensor system. Besides, the newly developed approach can be extended to print the sensors on the glass fiber prepreg directly without the substrate PET that could easier to realize the manufacturing of the multifunction composite.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Lu, Languang, et al. "A review on the key issues for lithium-ion battery management in electric vehicles." *Journal of power sources* 226 (2013): 272-288.
- [2] Feng, Xuning, et al. "Thermal runaway features of large format prismatic lithium ion battery using extended volume accelerating rate calorimetry." *Journal of power sources* 255 (2014): 294-301.
- [3] Abraham, D. P., et al. "Diagnostic examination of thermally abused high-power lithium-ion cells." *Journal of power sources* 161.1 (2006): 648-657.
- [4] Fan, Jiang, and Steven Tan. "Studies on charging lithium-ion cells at low temperatures." *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 153.6 (2006): A1081-A1092.
- [5] Waldmann, Thomas, et al. "Temperature dependent ageing mechanisms in Lithium-ion batteries—A Post-Mortem study." *Journal of Power Sources* 262 (2014): 129-135.
- [6] Bandhauer, Todd M., Srinivas Garimella, and Thomas F. Fuller. "A critical review of thermal issues in lithium-ion batteries." *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 158.3 (2011): R1-R25.
- [7] Xing, Yinjiao, et al. "Battery management systems in electric and hybrid vehicles." *Energies* 4.11 (2011): 1840-1857.
- [8] Hannan, Mohammad A., et al. "A review of lithium-ion battery state of charge estimation and management system in electric vehicle applications: Challenges and recommendations." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 78 (2017): 834-854.
- [9] Andrea, Davide. *Battery management systems for large lithium ion battery packs*. Artech house, 2010
- [10] Ando, Bruno, and Salvatore Baglio. "All-inkjet printed strain sensors." *IEEE Sensors Journal* 13.12 (2013): 4874-4879.
- [11] Abbas, Amal, and Inayat Bajwa. "Inkjet Printing of Ag Nanoparticles using Dimatix Inkjet Printer, No 1." (2017).
- [12] Correia, Vítor, et al. "Development of inkjet printed strain sensors." *Smart Materials and Structures* 22.10 (2013): 105028.
- [13] <https://www.sigmaaldrich.com/catalog/product/aldrich/901083?lang=en®ion=GB> [accessed 06.03.2019].
- [14] Courbat, J., et al. "Inkjet printing on paper for the realization of humidity and temperature sensors." *Solid-State Sensors, Actuators and Microsystems Conference (TRANSDUCERS)*, 2011 16th International. IEEE, 2011.